

Supplemental Figure 4

SI Figure 4: Examination of TLR-4 expression following HDE exposure. Western blots were used to detect protein level of TLR-4 in small (ileum) and large (cecum, proximal and distal colon) intestinal epithelial cells of saline-controlled and HDE-exposed mice. Densitometry of the bands were normalized to beta-actin and is expressed as a ratio. After 15 days of HDE exposure, the expression of TLR-4 was elevated in the proximal colon (unpaired t-test, $p=0.0303$, $n=5-6$ /group). TLR-4 expression was unaltered in the ileum, cecum, and distal colon ($p<0.05$, $n=5-6$ /group).